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Russell W. Chesney, M. D.

Prof. Russell W. Chesney

In this section, the editor, Dr. Al-Mosawi, invites a distinguished physician to contribute to the New Iraqi Journal of Medicine on a subject that is considered of interest to our readers. In this issue, Professor Chesney kindly wrote a paper about pediatric training and certification in the USA.

Dr. Chesney, a native of Knoxville, Tennessee, received his AB in Biology from Harvard College in 1963. He then attended the University of Rochester, where he took a year-out Fellowship in Renal Physiology and received his M.D. with Honors in 1968. He was a Pediatric Resident in the Harriet Lane Service at The Johns Hopkins Hospital from 1968-70 and 1972-73. From 1970-72, he was a Clinical Associate in Renal Biochemistry at the NIH (NICHD). He took a Fellowship in Pediatric Nephrology and Biochemical Genetics at the Montreal Children's Hospital of McGill University from 1973-75.

In 1975, he joined the faculty of the University of Wisconsin as a clinician-scientist in nephrology engaging in renal biochemical research and rose to Professor in 1981. In 1985, he became Professor and Vice Chair of Pediatrics at the University of California, Davis. He was appointed LeBonheur Professor and Chair of Pediatrics in 1988 at the University of Tennessee Health Sciences Center in Memphis, his current position.

Dr. Chesney became a member of the Society for Pediatric Research in 1976 and served as President from 1986-1987. A member of the American Pediatric Society, he has served on the Council since 1996 and was President from 2002-2003. He has participated in the Annual PAS meetings since 1972 and has presented many abstracts, sponsored others, served as a program moderator on numerous occasions and participated in plenary sessions and educational workshops. He has served as an officer of other organizations including the Midwest Society for Pediatric Research (Secretary-Treasurer, President), American Society of Pediatric Nephrology (Secretary-Treasurer, President) and Tennessee Chapter of the AAP (Council, President).

Dr. Chesney is a Diplomate and Member of the American Board of Pediatrics, serving on its Sub-Board in Nephrology and is currently Chair of the Board of Directors and Research Advisory Committee. He has also served as President and Vice President of the American Pediatric Society. He has been Secretary Treasurer and was President of the Association of Medical School Pediatric Department Chairs (AMSPDC) through January 2003. He has served on numerous national committees including the Pediatric Scientist Development Program Steering and Selection Committee, Scientific Advisory Committee of the National Kidney Foundation, National Kidney and Urology Diseases Advisory Board, General Medicine B Study Section (NIH), VA Merit Review

His ongoing research interests are in the areas of the 1) regulation of renal amino acid transport, 2) exploring gene-nutrient, transcriptional and translational mechanisms in regulating transporter synthesis, 3) inherited renal tubular disorders and 4) the physiology, biochemistry and of clinical application of vitamin D metabolites to childhood disorders of bone and mineral metabolism. He has published over 300 original peer-reviewed articles and 190 chapters. He is involved in the education of medical students, residents, post graduate fellows. He served as Vice Chair of the Future of Pediatric Education Task Force which

Committee in Nephrology (Chair) and several AAP Councils including Committee on Pediatric Research (Chair), Committee on Pediatric Education (Chair), Council in Federal Government Affairs and Board of the Children's Center for Health Research. He also serves as a member of the Public Policy Council of the

Federation of Pediatric Organizations. He also serves on the Child Health Finance Committee of the National Association of Children's Hospitals and Related Institutions and its Board of Directors. He has served on many editorial boards and served as Editor of Pediatric Nephrology and is currently Consulting Editor of Pediatrics.

recently published its findings concerning the lifelong education of pediatricians in the new century.

Dr. Chesney has received the E. Mead Johnson Award, the Nutrition Award of the AAP, the Founders Award of the Southern SPR, the Joseph St. Geme Leadership Award, the Henry Barnett Award and has been selected as a visiting professor at numerous medical schools.

He is married to Dr. P. Joan Chesney, a distinguished expert in pediatric infectious disease. They have three children.

The Training and Certification of Pediatricians in the United States of America

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The Training Process for General and Subspecialty Pediatrics

The concept of residency training in the discipline of pediatrics has evolved over the past 95 years in the United States, resulting in a highly defined and organized training program of 36 months that prepares medical school graduates to become general pediatricians. Individuals who wish to be trained in a subspecialty, such as nephrology, will usually train for an additional 36 months in a fellowship. After training in general pediatrics and in subspecialty pediatrics in a prescribed and approved training program, those individuals may then sit for an exam, which certifies them as having achieved a certain standard. At present, there exist approximately 200 three-year pediatric residency programs of between 4 and 36 residents per year. Currently, 3000 trainees per year are in these programs. Of the 200 programs; approximately 125 are located within the medical United States and Puerto Rico. Approximately 75 programs are found in academic schools of the centers not physically located in but often affiliated with a medic. In addition, several residencies are located in military hospitals of the U.S. Army, U.S. Navy, and the U.S. Air Force. All residency sites have a program director and faculty consisting of general pediatricians and

subspecialty pediatricians. Among the subspecialties represented are neonatology, cardiology, neurology, allergy and immunology, critical care, developmental and neurodevelopmental pediatrics, endocrinology, nephrology, gastroenterology, genetics, infectious disease, pulmonology, hematology/oncology, and emergency medicine the requirements of a pediatric residency program are governed by the Residency Review Committee (RRC) of the Accreditation Council on Graduate Medical Education (ACGME). These requirements govern the fundamental makeup of each residency in each medical discipline (internal medicine, surgery, psychiatry, etc.) and are divided into institutional and specific specialty (e.g., pediatrics) guidelines. These requirements are reviewed every 5 years and are generally vetted by a number of pediatric organizations including the American Academy of Pediatrics, the American Board of Pediatrics, the American Pediatric Society, the Society for Pediatric Research the Ambulatory Pediatric Association and the Association of Pediatric Program directors. While the RRC promulgates the requirements, these other societies evaluate and make

both general and specific comments. By a process of compromise, new guidelines are established, published, and then approved by the ACGME.

An important role of the Pediatric RRC is to visit each program on site at least once every 5 years. If all program requirements are met, then the program is approved. Candidates for a pediatric residency will obviously wish to train in an approved residency program.

The 3-year residency has graded responsibilities each year. The first year a resident or intern functions in inpatient and outpatient rotations as the most junior trainee. He or she must be a graduate of a medical school and must have passed the USMLE (United States Medical Licensing Examination) parts I, II and III.

The internship year is possibly the most important in all of U.S. medical education, because the intern is the individual with the most direct responsibility for his/h and it is a continuous learning year. Rotations are generally for one month, and include rotations in the inpatient service, the preterm nursery, the normal neonatal nursery, the emergency department and outpatient rotations. During the second year, residents will spend months as a supervisory resident on an inpatient service, more time in the emergency department, electives in pediatric subspecialties, and possibly more time in the preterm nursery. During the 36-month residency, there are required rotations in behavioral and developmental pediatrics, adolescent medicine, and a pediatric intensive care unit. During the 36 months, no more than 6 months can be spent in the intensive care unit and the neonatal intensive care unit.

The third year of the residency is spent in a supervisory role on the inpatient units, in the nursery and in the

outpatient department, with the remaining months being spent on electives. After the 36 months of training, the program director approves each resident to sit for the American Board of Pediatrics examination.

Each year one to two individuals are chosen as the Chief Resident(s). These individuals play an important teaching and administrative role. In most programs, this individual is in his/her 4th year of training.

All residents receive a salary that is paid by the teaching hospital. The hospital then recovers this funding in the form of graduate medical education funding from the medical system, an insurance program that covers all individuals over 65 years of age or from U.S. government funding provided to children's hospitals.

WHY PHYSICIANS ARE CERTIFIED BY BOARDS

The concept of Board Certification of a physician in a discipline dates back more than 80 years. A certificate was awarded for life and indicated that the certificate holder had taken and passed a written examination and, often, an oral examination. This board certification indicates that a physician has met a national standard. The "Boards" of the major disciplines, such as Pediatrics, Medicine, Surgery, etc are bound together under the American Board of Medical Specialists (ABMS) which supervises 24 specialty boards.

The programs in which ABMS trainees are trained are carefully critiqued and evaluated by the ACGME – the Accreditation Council for Graduate Medical Education. The Residency Review Committees (RRC) are

appointed by the ACGME and review all residencies. An important concept to bear in mind is that individual physicians, are certified by “Boards” based upon their knowledge, skills, and attitudes, and that residency programs are accredited by the RRC and, hence, the ACGME and not by individual “Boards”. The individual physician is certified by the following process: training for a designated time period in an approved residency program, completing a prescribed curriculum, being approved to sit for a certifying examination by a program director, and passing a secure examination in a testing center. As time h the 1930’s, new concepts have been incorporated. Key among these are that the individual trainees have the attitudes and moral behavior required of an excellent physician (as attested by the program director) and that the certificate is time-limited; physicians must recertify to maintain their Board status. Similarly, training program required to renew their status with the RRC at five-year intervals, thus assuring that residency program development is ongoing. Most critical, however, is that the Board assures the public of the knowledge, skills, and attitudes of each physician who receives a certificate. Since the Board certifies physicians, it must have a slightly distant and objective relationship with medical-led professional societies. Hence, the American Board of Pediatrics is separate from the American Academy of Pediatrics, the American Board of Internal Medicine is separate from the American College of Physicians, and

so forth. Similarly, sub-boards are independent of subspecialty societies, e. g., ASN/ASPN, etc. All boards have non-physician members who represent the views of the public.

A specialty board can develop a subspecialty board. For instance, the American Board of Pediatrics (ABP) certifies pediatric nephrologists through the Sub-Board o Pediatric Nephrology. It is the role of the ACGME, through the RRC, to approve the length and content of each Nephrology fellowship program. This is how each program receives its accreditation. However, the examination that must be passed by each trainee is written by the members of the Sub-Board of Pediatric Nephrology and supervised by the American Board of Pediatrics. This process of training and certification is not influenced by professional societies or by pharmaceutical companies. The fee for the examination is paid by the trainee. This process assures the public of lack of undue influence by the profession on the certification process.

The Boards of clinical disciplines also have “third-tier” examination and certificates. “Third-tier” is defined as specialized skills within a sub-board of a discipline Under the American Board of Pediatrics are third-tier Boards in Toxicology and in Laboratory Medicine. A third-tier certificate also exists in Cardiac Electrophysiology within Internal Medicine/Cardiology. The American Society for Transplantation (AST) has been evaluating, approving, accrediting and credentialing fellowship programme in renal transplantation in Internal Medicine. If there is a need for third-tier certification in renal transplantation, the Board process

could serve as a mechanism by which the discipline of renal transplantation could be evaluated. While a third-tier certification process requires several timely steps and approval at several levels (Task Force of ABP,

APP Board of Directors, ABMS, ASPN members), serves as a mechanism of certification that ensures impartiality and is in keeping with established standards in the academic pediatric community.

In conclusion, the certification process involves a series of steps by which individual physicians can be evaluated by a specialty board, and the training program in which that physician trains is accredited by a residency review committee that is supervised by the ACGME. This process has been in place for many years (80+), has served pediatrics well, and is now being emulated by organized medicine in the nations of the European Union. Most importantly, the established processes ensure an important served pediatrics well, and is now being emulated by organized medicine in the nations of the European Union.

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